

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FUTURE PROSPECTS OF BUDGET DECENTRALIZATION AND "GREEN" ECONOMY REFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This article analyzes the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan regarding budget decentralization. Based on the trends in the world budget practice, UN Sustainable Development Goals, suggestions and recommendations have been developed by the author on the necessary reforms to increase the financial independence of budgets of the budget system in the future.

Keywords. Budget decentralization, SDG, local budget, financial independence of local budget, state of socio-economic development of regions.

INTRODUCTION

The Republic of Uzbekistan is rapidly integrating into the world economy at a new stage of economic development. Countries of the world are developing development strategies based on the UN Sustainable Development Goals. As the most important directions in this direction, reducing poverty and achieving climate change are gaining importance.

The decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP#436 of December 2, 2022 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of reforms aimed at the transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy by 2030" is proof of our opinion. Based on this decision, in accordance with the obligations of the state budget in 2021, "to strengthen measures to combat climate change, to increase the energy efficiency of the economy by 20% in the next 5 years, as well as to increase the share of renewable energy sources to 25%, and thereby by 2030 it is planned to reduce the amount of greenhouse gases released into the air by 35% from the level of 2010" [1].

Among the UN member states, Uzbekistan also approved the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In 2018, taking into account the obligations under the SDGs, the Government of Uzbekistan approved national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030 and initiated institutional changes to support them. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 83 of February 21, 2022 "On additional measures to accelerate the implementation of national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030" approved national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030 [2]. In 2020, two-thirds of public spending is related to financing the national Sustainable Development Goals [3].

LITERATURE REVIEWS

Classical economists Musgrave; Oates budget federalism is considered as three important functions of the public sector: increasing economic efficiency; achieving macroeconomic stability; income redistribution. According to the American economist Richard Musgrave, central government authorities should take responsibility for the last two functions, local government

authorities are much closer to citizens, have more complete information about citizens, and must ensure the effectiveness of social benefits provided to them in their area[4].

An important factor of budget decentralization is explained by the fact that the provision of social benefits increases production efficiency [5]. The efficiency of providing most of the decentralized social benefits is relatively high compared to the centralized provision, because the state authority in the lower-ranking areas can ensure the improvement of the welfare of the local population due to the full satisfaction of the individual desire of the population (preference-matching argument).

In the conditions of decentralization, the efficiency of production can also be higher. Local government bodies, knowing the needs of citizens, having the experience of providing relevant social benefits, will have the opportunity to provide these benefits at a low cost [6]. Economists see the expansion of horizontal and vertical budget competition as another advantage of budget decentralization. This, in turn, limits the reduction of the public sector and its "predatory" incentives[7].

In addition, in the presence of strong democratic institutions (freedom of election and election, rule of law, effective parliamentarism system) in the society, budget decentralization expands the accountability of local government bodies to citizens and serves to improve the quality of management [8].

Issues related to climate change are widely studied by foreign and domestic economists. In particular, the local economist A. Islamkulov in his researches says that "unfavorable weather as a result of climate change also destroys the ability to fulfill obligations to tax payers. Based on this, when a taxpayer suffers a loss as a result of a technological disaster or other insurmountable circumstances, the extension of tax payment terms is consistent with the principle of social justice of taxes. In these cases, it is appropriate to present the expert opinion of the authorized body (organization) on the value of the damage caused to the taxpayer as a result of natural disasters, technological disaster or other circumstances of force majeure" [9].

In Uzbekistan, the issues of climate change financing, additional incentives for waste collection, sorting and processing through taxes have not been sufficiently studied.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In 2022, in order to promote the integration of climate issues with budget planning and the budget process, the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, with the support of the United Nations Development Program and the French Development Agency (FTA), carried out the "Analysis and Institutional Assessment of State Expenditures in the Field of Climate Change" (CPEIR) and with climate methodology for determining related costs was developed. In order to test the proposed methodology, the determination of costs related to climate change was carried out based on the information on the implementation of the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022. In the course of this designation exercise, it was investigated whether the cost item is climate change-related or independent, positive, negative, or non-impact, as well as climate change mitigation, adaptation, or mixed. In 2022, 30,016.3 billion soums or 13% of the total expenditures of the State budget were

attributed to climate change, and the rest were included in non-impact expenditures, that is, it is not possible to determine whether the expenditures have no impact on climate change or not [4]. In FY 2023, 41,625.8 billion soums or 14.8% of the state budget expenditures were attributed to climate change, the rest were included in non-impact expenditures, that is, it is not possible to determine whether the expenditures do not affect climate change or are related [10].

Another aspect, according to our observations and studies, is the effectiveness of budget system execution and its control, and in 2024, "the task of controlling the correct spending of 313 trillion soums provided for in the current year's budget was assigned." In order to evaluate the effectiveness of funds allocated to 37 ministries and agencies, target indicators are set within 120 programs"[11].

As mentioned above, the study of the state of the share of local budget expenditures in the state budget expenditures makes it possible to assess the reforms implemented for the purpose of budget decentralization. Therefore, we analyze the share of local budget expenditures in state budget expenditures in Figure 1 below.

Fig.#1. Dynamics of changes in the share of local budget expenditures in state budget expenditures
By author

Note. ESB – total expenditures of the Government budget; ELB – total expenditures of the local budgets

Analyzing the data of Figure 1, the share of local budget expenditures in state budget expenditures in 2019 was 44 percent. This situation is explained by the fact that in 2019, 36 budget organizations financed from the republican budget will be provided with funds from the local budgets of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city, and 3 budget organizations will be transferred from the republican budget to district and city local budgets [11]. In 2020, compared to 2019, the share of local budget expenses in the state budget expenses decreased by 11.4 percentage points. This situation started in the republic from 2020, when the state budget was approved by law,

and the practice of providing budget funds with funds in the form of first and second level distributors was introduced. In addition, as a result of the coronavirus pandemic, budgets of the budget system were optimized, local budgets were not excluded from this optimization [12]. In 2021, an increase in the share of local budget expenditures by 2.2 percentage points compared to 2020, the recovery of the economy after the pandemic began, and also, starting from 2021, the practice of budgeting based on the target indicators of State programs and budget expenditures for 2021 began to be used, from February 1, 2021, the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm It is appropriate to note

that the amount of one-time financial assistance to needy families in the region was increased from 434,000 soums to 1,085,000 soums[13]. In fiscal year 2022, it increased by 2.9 percentage points compared to 2021. This increase is determined that starting from January 1, 2022, payments for state purchases made at the expense of budget funds (except for purchases made on the basis of import contracts) will be made only by issuing electronic invoices [14]. This practice provided an opportunity for efficient, accurate and targeted implementation of state budget funds, including local budget funds. Also, from this financial year, in order to reduce the consumption of electricity in budget organizations, replacing electrical devices with "smart" lamps in the administrative buildings of local governments, ministries and agencies, introducing public-private partnership and outsourcing mechanisms in the field of landscaping have been set as priorities, and they have been consistently implemented. These positive results can be seen in the decrease of the share of local budgets in 2023 compared to 2022 by 1.2 percentage points. Also, in 2023, specific mechanisms were created to provide free meals to first-fourth graders in the regions, to establish public control over the spending of funds allocated for these purposes, and to prevent corruption factors.

In conclusion, systematic measures are being implemented regarding the impact of achieving financial independence of local budgets through the effective implementation of local budgets.

At the same time, considerable work has been done in the republic on the harmonization of the state budget expenditures with the goals of sustainable

development, but the system of encouraging business entities engaged in the collection, removal, sorting and processing of waste by means of taxes has not been sufficiently created.

At this point, if we refer to advanced foreign experience, in Germany, "waste disposal and processing is a separate branch of the German economy. More than 240,000 people are employed in this network, and the annual turnover of the network exceeds 80 billion euros. In Germany, each federal state has its own waste law, municipal levy laws, rules and regulations on municipal public order violations and fines. In Germany, "inhabitants pay from 10 to 50 euros per person depending on the federal land for the removal of household waste in the payment of general utility bills[15].

There are about 66 factories with a total production capacity of 26.5 million tons per year and thermal processing of waste, and about 30 power plants that work on the basis of incineration of solid household waste. According to calculations, the heat release due to waste incineration is 10 MJ (megajoules) per 1 kg or 2.78 kWh. The country's financial sector sees recycling as a sustainable business. "Green" bonds in the amount of 400 million euros were issued to finance "green" projects.

In the United States, states also have special tax credits and preferences for waste disposal and recycling (See Tab.#1). Analyzing the data in Table 1, different tax incentives and preferences are applied to business entities engaged in waste collection, removal, sorting and processing activities in some states of the USA.

Table #1.
Tax credits and preferences for business entities engaged in the collection, removal, sorting and processing of waste in certain states of the USA [12]

State	Description
Arizona	Recycling equipment income tax credit for individuals and corporations equaling 10 percent of the installed cost of the equipment. Equipment must process postconsumer recyclables or produce finished products composed of at least 25 percent postconsumer recycled materials.
Arkansas	Recycling equipment income tax credit equaling 30 percent of the equipment costs. Equipment must handle at least 10 percent postconsumer solid waste.
Delaware, Florida	Recycling investment tax credit totaling \$500 for each \$100,000 invested.
Georgia	Personal income tax credit for investment in recycling facilities, machinery, or equipment. Amount of credit is equal to 3, 5, or 8 percent (based on tiers) of the qualified investment.
Hawaii	Recycling equipment sales tax reduction of between 0.5 and 4 percent.
Iowa	Personal and real property tax exemptions for machinery and equipment used for recycling or reprocessing of paper, cardboard, or plastic products. 100 percent sales tax exemption for purchases of industrial machinery, equipment, computers, and replacement parts used in the recycling or reprocessing of waste products.
Idaho	Recycling equipment income tax credit of up to 20 percent of equipment costs but not exceeding \$30,000 per year. Requires that 90 percent of the equipment's product be made from recyclables.
Kentucky	Recycling equipment personal income tax credit of up to 50 percent of the equipment costs. Recycling equipment sales and use tax exemption. Includes equipment used to collect, separate, compress, bale, shred, or handle waste materials for recycling.
Montana	Recycling equipment income tax credit of 25 percent for the first \$250,000 invested, 15 percent for the next \$250,000, and 5 percent on the next \$500,000.
Wisconsin	Recycling property tax exemption for machinery and equipment, including parts, used exclusively and directly in waste reduction or recycling.

In summary, states have different approaches to waste collection, removal, sorting and disposal based on their level of socio-economic development, environmental conditions in the state, and potential for waste production.

Our research shows that the private sector in Uzbekistan is not enough to invest in this production. Therefore, in our opinion, it is appropriate to set profit tax and social tax at the rate of 1% in cases where the income received by business entities engaged in waste collection, removal, sorting and processing activities in the regions is not less than 90% of their total income at the end of the tax period.

With the implementation of this practice in Uzbekistan, "as a result of burning about 250,000 tons of waste per year, it is possible to produce about 125 million kWh of electricity and add 36.88 billion soums to the budget."

CONCLUSION

Developing development strategies based on the UN Sustainable Development Goals. As the most important directions in this direction, reducing poverty and achieving climate change are gaining importance.

In order to further increase the powers of local councils in the field of budgeting, it is advisable to fully introduce reporting to local councils about the effective and targeted spending of budget funds and the practical results of expenditures by the distributors of regional budget funds.

By further developing the system of target indicators, going without deviating from the practice of result-oriented budgeting makes it possible to achieve the tax-budgetary policy of Keynes in terms of budget expenditures.

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